

EFFECTIVENESS OF PHOSPHODIESTERASE INHIBITORS IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14940233>

Abstract. *The purpose of the research is to evaluate phosphodiesterase inhibitors' clinical and functional outcomes in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease patients. The study included 130 participants, comprising 110 COPD patients and 20 healthy controls. Patients were divided into two main groups based on disease classification (A/B and C/D) and further stratified into subgroups based on treatment received. The effectiveness of treatment was assessed through clinical symptoms (cough, sputum production, dyspnea), CAT scores, and lung function parameters (FEV1 and FEV1/FVC). After one month of treatment, patients receiving phosphodiesterase inhibitors demonstrated a significant reduction in cough severity, sputum production, and dyspnea scores. CAT scores improved significantly in the treatment subgroups (1A and 2A), with a 1.3-fold decrease. FEV1 improved by 7.1% in subgroup 1A and 7.3% in subgroup 2A, whereas the control subgroups (1B and 2B) showed smaller improvements (2.7% and 3.8%, respectively). The FEV1/FVC ratio remained largely unchanged. Phosphodiesterase inhibitors in COPD patients resulted in significant clinical and functional improvements within one month. These findings suggest phosphodiesterase inhibitors may be an effective treatment option for reducing inflammation and improving lung function in COPD patients. Long-term studies are needed to investigate their impact on disease progression further.*

Keywords: *COPD, phosphodiesterase inhibitors, lung function, inflammation, COPD, FEV1, CAT score, bronchodilator therapy.*

In COPD, the immune reactivity state of the body plays a crucial role in the pathogenesis of airway inflammation. Immune alterations are primarily associated with increased neutrophils, macrophages, and CD8+ T-lymphocytes [9]. Key mediators of chronic airway inflammation in COPD include interleukin (IL)-6, tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α , and IL-8. Cytokines exhibit various biological activities, facilitating intercellular interactions in immune and inflammatory responses. They function as immune system mediators, regulating the strength and duration of immune responses and the nature and intensity of inflammation [2,7]. Phosphodiesterase inhibitors have long been recognized for their high anti-inflammatory efficacy [1, 3, 8]. Based on evidence-based medicine principles, these inhibitors have been included in the updated GOLD recommendations as a new class of drugs for COPD treatment. The first representative of this new drug class is roflumilast [6]. Phosphodiesterase inhibitors reduce inflammation in COPD. Additionally, in patients with frequent exacerbations (stages 3 and 4) and chronic bronchitis, using roflumilast combined with oral corticosteroids reduces the number of exacerbations [10]. Phosphodiesterase inhibitors are specific enzyme blockers responsible for inflammation in COPD and belong to the group of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. Doxofylline acts on specific

phosphodiesterase subtypes (A, B, and D). Each subtype regulates cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP) metabolism, preventing its conversion to the inactive form (AMP), which is involved in inflammation and immune cell activity. This, in turn, leads to reduced activation of effector proteins through cell protein kinase activity inhibition [5]. Consequently, the release of inflammatory mediators decreases, and neutrophils and CD8+ T-lymphocytes become less active in initiating inflammation. The specific effect of phosphodiesterase inhibitors on cAMP and the increased quantity of these isoforms in inflammatory cells and structures make them a key therapeutic target for chronic inflammation in COPD. The use of doxofylline reduces lung-specific inflammation by decreasing the dysfunction of leukocytes, endothelial cells, and fibroblasts. Doxofylline positively affects the mucociliary apparatus, prevents fibrosis, and inhibits the development of emphysema and pulmonary vascular remodeling. The improvement in lung function observed with doxofylline is associated with its effect on neutrophil count. Studies have shown a direct proportional relationship between lung function decline and increased neutrophil count in sputum. Increased neutrophil levels have been observed in patients with airway obstruction and chronic sputum production. Therefore, phosphodiesterase inhibitors are clinically effective, well-tolerated drugs with minimal side effects. However, the current literature lacks studies examining their impact on systemic inflammation in COPD based on disease category. A literature review suggests that further research is needed to assess the long-term outcomes of these medications in COPD patients [4].

Research Materials and Methods: All patients included in the study were informed about the research plan, and their written consent was obtained. The diagnosis of COPD was established based on ICD-10, clinical protocols, and clinical guidelines. A total of 130 participants were included in the study: 110 COPD patients and 20 healthy controls. The COPD patients were divided into two groups: Group 1 (53 patients) included those classified as types A and B, while Group 2 (57 patients) included those classified as types C and D. Based on the treatment type, the following subgroups were formed: Subgroup A: Patients receiving 400 mg of phosphodiesterase inhibitor (doxofylline) daily in addition to bronchodilator therapy (subgroups 1A and 2A). Subgroup B: Patients receiving bronchodilator therapy according to the GOLD treatment scheme (subgroups 1B and 2B). Inflammation markers were assessed using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). Serological analysis included IL-6 and IL-8 ("Vector-Best," Russia), C-reactive protein (CRP), and TNF- α ("Biochemmack," Austria). ELISA sample significance intervals ranged from 2 to 50 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Patients admitted to the hospital received standard treatment, including inhaled combinations of long-acting and short-acting bronchodilators during exacerbations (e.g., "Berodual N," containing 21 μg of ipratropium bromide monohydrate and 50 μg of fenoterol hydrobromide per inhalation dose). Group 2 patients received glucocorticoids (prednisolone 30-40 mg/day for 5-7 days) when indicated. According to N.R. Anthonisen's criteria, antibiotic therapy was administered based on sensitivity in cases of worsening dyspnea, increased sputum volume, and purulence. Antibiotics included moxifloxacin (400 mg/day), amoxicillin/clavulanate (625 mg twice daily), or cefixime (200 mg twice daily) for five days. If oxygen saturation fell below 88%, oxygen therapy was provided using a Venturi mask at 1-2 L/min until saturation reached 88-92%. For daily treatment based on GOLD risk categories, the following medications were used: Long-acting muscarinic antagonist (tiotropium bromide 18 μg once daily) or Long-acting β_2 -agonist (formoterol 4.5-12 μg once daily) or a combination of

both. Patients in subgroups 1A and 2A also received 400 mg of a phosphodiesterase inhibitor (doxofylline) daily for 12 months. The study results were analyzed using Statistica 10.0 software.

Research Results: Analysis of treatment outcomes one month after initiation showed a significant reduction in clinical symptoms. Table 1 presents changes in clinical and functional parameters after one month of treatment.

Table 1

Changes in clinical and functional indicators in COPD patients one month after treatment

Indicators	Groups	Pre-treatment indicators	Post-treatment indicators (1 month)
Cough (score)	1A (n=25)	1.4	1.1*
	1B (n=28)	1.6	1.2*
	2A (n=27)	2.2	1.6*
	2B (n=30)	2.2	1.7*
Sputum (score)	1A (n=25)	1.6	1.4*
	1B (n=28)	1.8	1.4*
	2A (n=27)	2.2	1.8*
	2B (n=30)	2.3	2*
Dyspnea by mMRC	1A (n=25)	1.2	1*
	1B (n=28)	1.2	1*
	2A (n=27)	2.4	2.1*
	2B (n=30)	2.5	2.1*
CAT assessment test (score)	1A (n=25)	10.2	7.9*
	1B (n=28)	10.4	8.4*
	2A (n=27)	21.5	17.8*
	2B (n=30)	22.3	19.8*#
FEV1 (%)	1A (n=25)	61.3	68.4*
	1B (n=28)	60.8	63.5
	2A (n=27)	43.7	48.2*
	2B (n=30)	42.5	46.3
FEV1/FVC (%)	1A (n=25)	61.6	64.2
	1B (n=28)	60.5	62.7
	2A (n=27)	55.7	57.6
	2B (n=30)	53.8	56.8

Note: * - Statistically significant difference compared to pre-treatment values ($p < 0.05$), # - Statistically significant difference between subgroup A and B ($p < 0.05$)

Table 1 shows that cough severity significantly decreased after one month of treatment. Improvement in dyspnea was more pronounced in Group 1. CAT scores showed a 1.3-fold reduction in subgroups 1A and 2A (7.9 and 8.4, respectively) and a 1—to 1.2-fold reduction in subgroups 2A and 2B (17.8 and 19.8, respectively). After six months, patients in subgroup 1A showed a 1.4-point decrease in CAT scores compared to subgroup 1B. Dyspnea was less pronounced in subgroup 2A compared to subgroup 2B. The most significant changes were observed in breathlessness severity and CAT scores. After six months of treatment, FEV1 showed

further improvement, with subgroup 1A displaying a 9% increase compared to one-month results, maintaining this level at 12 months. In contrast, subgroup B showed a 5% increase at six months and an additional 2% increase at 12 months.

Conclusion: Patients treated with phosphodiesterase inhibitors demonstrated a sustained improvement in lung function over 12 months, particularly in reducing breathlessness and improving CAT scores. Further long-term studies are warranted to explore their role in COPD management.

REFERENCES

1. Avdeev S.N. Phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitors: new perspectives in anti-inflammatory therapy for COPD // *Pharmateca*. - 2018. - Vol. 257, No. 4. - P. 101-111.
2. Ketlinsky S.A. et al. Cytokines // *St. Petersburg: Foliant*. - 2013. - 552 p.
3. Knyazheskaya N.P. Phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitors - anti-inflammatory drugs in COPD treatment // *Russian Medical Journal*. - 2018. - No. 29. - P. 1460-1464.
4. Kulik E.G. The impact of anti-inflammatory therapy on the long-term prognosis and course of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease of different risk levels // *Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Medical Sciences, 14.01.25 Pulmonology*. - Blagoveshchensk. - 2019. - 135 p.
5. Skvortsov V.V. et al. Roflumilast in the treatment of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) // *Scientific and Practical Electronic Journal "Alley of Science"*. - 2022. - No. 11(74).
6. Shishkina E.S. Clinical and diagnostic significance of assessing and correcting cytokine status in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and ischemic heart disease // *Dissertation for the degree of Candidate of Medical Sciences, 14.01.04 Internal Diseases*. - Voronezh. - 2017. - 128 p.
7. Yarilin A.A. *Immunology* // Moscow: GEOTAR-Media. - 2015. - 752 p.
8. Beghe B. et al. Phosphodiesterase-4 inhibitor therapy for lung diseases // *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine*. - 2018. - No. 188(3). - P. 271-278.
9. Chung K.F. Cytokines in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease // *European Respiratory Journal*. - 2016. - Vol. 18. - P. 50-59.
10. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease. *Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease* [Electronic Resource]. - 2015. - URL: <http://www.goldcopd.org>.